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(57) Abstract :

Artificial intelligence Approach to Analyse the Efficiency of Photosynthesis of Plants on the Biophysics Aspects of Agriculture is the proposed invention. The proposed invention focuses on photosynthesis of plants in growth of agricultural sustainability. The algorithms of Artificial Intelligence are used for the purposed of predicting the Biophysics aspects of agriculture.

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